

Original Research

Determinants of Tax Compliance for Individual Taxpayers: The Moderating Role of Tax Consultants at West Mataram Tax Office

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the influence of understanding tax regulations, willingness to pay taxes, quality of tax office services, and tax sanctions on the fulfilment of individual taxpayers' tax obligations, by analyzing the role of tax consultants as a moderating variable. The research sample was taken using a purposive sampling technique from 100 individual taxpayers registered at the West Mataram Pratama Tax Service Office. The collected data were analyzed using Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) with SPSS 27. The results showed that understanding tax regulations, willingness to pay taxes, and tax sanctions had a positive and significant effect on the fulfilment of tax obligations. However, the quality of tax office services did not have a significant effect, and the role of tax consultants was unable to moderate the influence of understanding tax regulations, willingness to pay taxes, quality of tax office services, and tax sanctions on the fulfilment of individual taxpayers' tax obligations. This study implies that the fulfilment of individual taxpayers' tax obligations is more effectively carried out through strengthening the understanding of tax regulations, strengthening willingness, and enforcing tax sanctions. Meanwhile, improving services is not yet effective in increasing compliance. In addition, based on the test results, it is necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of the role of tax consultants in supporting individual taxpayer compliance. This finding is also in line with major theories such as the Theory of Planned Behavior, attribution theory, compliance theory, and tax awareness theory.

Keywords: Service Quality, Tax Compliance, Tax Consultants, Tax Knowledge, Tax Penalties, Willingness to Pay.

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Introduction

Indonesia's national development aims to improve the welfare of its people, and to that end, the government continues to maximise state revenue. Among various sources of income, taxes play a central role as the backbone of state financing and spending, far exceeding the contribution of non-tax revenue. The strategic position of taxes is not only the basis of fiscal policy but is also reinforced by various scientific studies that consistently affirm their crucial role in supporting development, such as Noor Neilmaldrin (2022) and Latifah et al. (2021).

Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency (2024), from 2018 to 2024, the tax sector clearly dominated state revenue. Its contribution to the state budget averaged 79.16%, reaching 82.42% in 2024, despite an average increase of 14.14% from the previous year. However, the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 caused tax contributions to decline by 16.88%. This was reinforced by the Regulation of the Minister of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia (2020) PMK 44/PMK.03/2020 concerning tax incentives for taxpayers affected by the pandemic, as well as research (Rahmi Oktavia et al., 2022) showing a decline in contribution.

Given that taxes are the state's largest source of revenue, the Directorate General of Taxes (DGT) continues to implement various strategies to optimise revenue, both through extensification and intensification. Intensification is carried out through improving service quality, administrative supervision, and effective law enforcement (Dechan, 2020), (Maulana M, 2022), and (Hardiningsih & Yulianawati, 2011). However, to maximise tax revenue, it is not enough to rely solely on the role of the DGT; active participation from taxpayers themselves is also required (Suhendri, 2015).

The government has made various efforts to encourage this participation, one of which is tax regulation reform by implementing a self-assessment system since 1983, as stipulated in General provisions and tax procedures Article 12 paragraph (1), Law Number. 7 of 2022 concerning HPP, and Law Number. 6 of 2023. However, the implementation of this system has not been fully in line with the level of tax awareness and compliance in Indonesia, which continues to decline. The compliance ratio of non-employee taxpayers, for example, fell to 67.41% compared to 75.93% in the previous year (Muhammad Wildan, 2024).

This phenomenon of declining tax compliance is particularly noticeable at the local level, especially at the West Mataram Tax Office. As of 2023, out of a total of 148,697 registered taxpayers (51,371 non-employees and 97,326 employees), only 40,476 taxpayers, or around 27.22%, actively fulfilled their tax obligations. This means that around 72.78% of the total registered individual taxpayers have the potential to be effective taxpayers but do not fulfil their tax obligations, which falls under the intensification category. Thus, the level of tax compliance at the Mataram Barat Tax Office only reaches 27.22%. This can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Level of Tax Compliance of Registered Individual Taxpayer in 2017-2023

Year	Registered Individual Taxpayer			Individual Taxpayer Annual Tax Return			% Annual Tax Return
	Non-Employee	Employee	Total	Non-Employee	Employee	Total	
2017	16.401	73.632	90.033	3.703	35.749	39.452	43,82%
2018	17.615	77.312	94.927	3.781	37.038	40.819	43,00%
2019	18.949	80.741	99.690	3.599	34.150	37.749	37,87%
2020	46.674	84.367	131.041	3.464	39.426	42.890	32,73%
2021	47.931	88.322	136.253	3.393	35.765	39.158	28,74%
2022	49.495	92.712	142.207	3.436	35.434	38.870	27,33%
2023	51.371	97.326	148.697	4.146	36.330	40.476	27,22%

Source: General Affairs Division of the West Mataram Tax Office, compiled in 2025

The fulfilment of tax obligations by taxpayers is a reflection of the exercise of their tax rights and obligations. Various factors can influence the level of fulfilment of these obligations, both from the internal side of taxpayers and external factors. From the internal side of taxpayers, understanding tax regulations is fundamental. Understanding, defined as the ability to comprehend something correctly (Irwan, 2011), is believed to increase tax compliance (Manuba & Gayatri, 2017; Mangiwa & Asyik, 2023; Putri, 2022; (Kumala & Ayu, 2021), (Ramadhanty & Zulaikha, 2020). However, there are also contradictory findings that show that understanding tax regulations does not significantly affect the fulfilment of individual taxpayer obligations (Chandra & Waluyo, 2023), (Diah & Ode, 2019) and (Surbakti et al., 2024), indicating a complexity that requires further exploration. In addition, the willingness of taxpayers to fulfil their tax obligations is also very important. This willingness often stems from awareness and understanding of the benefits of taxation for national development (Yoga & Dewi, 2021; Youde & Lim, 2019), in line with Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (1991). Several studies support the significant influence of taxpayer willingness on tax compliance (Gusti et al., 2021) and (Diah & Ode, 2019), even linking it to moral principles, social norms, and ethical attitudes (Young et al., 2016). However, there are also studies that find that the willingness factor does not have a significant impact on tax compliance (Widayati & Nurlis, 2010) and (Wilda, 2015).

Furthermore, from an external perspective, the quality of service provided by the tax office plays an important role. Excellent service, covering physical aspects, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, can make it easier for taxpayers to fulfil their obligations (Sudiartana & Apriada, 2018). Various digital innovations such as e-Registration, e-Filing, e-Billing, e-Invoicing, and the Core Tax Administration System (CTAS), which will come into effect on 1 January 2025, are the government's efforts to improve service quality. Many studies support that service quality has a positive and significant impact on the fulfilment of tax obligations (Wilda, 2015), (Ramadhanty & Zulaikha, 2020), and (Azizah et al., 2016). However, there are also studies that conclude that the quality of tax office services has no effect on tax revenue performance or has an insignificant effect on tax compliance (Fauziah & Hidayat, 2022), (Kumala & Ayu,

2021). Another external factor that influences tax compliance is tax penalties. Administrative penalties, such as fines, interest, or surcharges, which are regulated in tax laws, are designed to have a deterrent effect. Fairly applied sanctions can increase tax compliance among taxpayers (Verboon & van Dijke, 2011), as taxpayers are more likely to comply if they perceive that sanctions will be more detrimental (Jatmiko, 2006), (Rahmayanti et al., 2020), (Wijaya, 2023). Research also supports that tax sanctions have a positive and significant effect on individual taxpayer tax compliance, namely (Yoga & Dewi, 2021) and (Tasmilah, 2021). However, this differs from the research conducted by Maxuel & Primastiwi (2021), which found that tax sanctions do not have a significant effect on tax compliance.

Given the complexity of these factors, the role of tax consultants is interesting to examine as a factor that has the potential to moderate the relationship between the proposed variables and the fulfilment of tax obligations. Tax consultants are professionals who provide tax consulting services to taxpayers, assisting them in exercising their rights and fulfilling their tax obligations in accordance with applicable regulations (Indonesian Minister of Finance, n.d.) based on PMK 111/PMK.03/2014 and PMK 175/PMK.01/2022. With their expertise and understanding of tax regulations, tax consultants can influence taxpayers to fulfil their tax obligations (Basuki, 2018; Fatimaleha et al., 2020; Nugraheni et al., 2021; Widiasih & Wiagustini, 2019).

Although the self-assessment system has been implemented with the hope of improving individual taxpayer tax compliance, the reality on the ground, particularly at the West Mataram Tax Office, shows that the level of individual taxpayer tax compliance still tends to decline. Based on previous studies, there are research gaps that underlie this study. First, the results of previous studies have been inconsistent. Second, previous studies used the role of tax consultants as an independent variable, but in this study, the role of tax consultants will be tested as a moderating variable. Third, previous studies used willingness to pay taxes as a dependent variable and moderating variable, but in this study, willingness to pay taxes will be an independent variable. Therefore, this study is a development of the studies by Manuba & Gayatri (2017) and Mangiwa & Asyik (2023), using the independent variables of understanding of tax regulations, willingness to pay taxes, quality of tax office services, and tax penalties, as well as tax compliance as the dependent variable. A significant difference from previous studies is the use of the role of tax consultants as a moderating variable, as well as the focus of the location and year of the study on taxpayers registered at the West Mataram Tax Office.

Research Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

The Effect of Understanding Tax Regulations on the Fulfilment of Individual Taxpayer Obligations

In the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), specific individual behaviour is influenced by three main factors: attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. A person's intention to act is largely determined by behavioural beliefs that shape attitudes, normative beliefs that shape subjective norms, and control beliefs that shape behavioural control. A good understanding of tax regulations greatly determines the attitudes, subjective norms, and behavioural control of Individual Taxpayers in fulfilling their tax obligations.

The theory of consciousness emphasises that an individual's understanding of something is influenced by their level of awareness of the importance of that knowledge in their life. In the context of taxation, individual taxpayer awareness of the importance of understanding tax regulations is key to encouraging compliance. Meanwhile, attribution theory explains that a person's behaviour is determined by internal and external factors. Understanding tax regulations is an internal factor that is perceived to influence taxpayer compliance.

Understanding tax regulations is a process for taxpayers to learn and apply tax rules in order to fulfil their obligations. A person will act positively if they have an understanding that is driven by motivation from tax laws. This basic understanding is very important because it affects the level of taxpayer compliance. Research (Manuba & Gayatri, 2017) shows that understanding tax regulations has a positive effect on taxpayer compliance. Similar results were found by Mangiwa & Asyik (2023) and Kumala & Ayu (2021), who stated that understanding has a significant influence on taxpayer willingness, as well as Silahi & Asalam (2022) and Ramadhanty & Zulaikha (2020), who found a positive and significant influence on taxpayer compliance. A person's behaviour is determined by internal and external factors. Understanding tax regulations is an internal factor that is perceived to influence taxpayer compliance.

Based on the description and results of previous studies, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H₁: Understanding tax regulations has a positive effect on the fulfilment of individual taxpayer obligations.

The Effect of Willingness to Pay Taxes on the Fulfilment of Individual Taxpayer Obligations

According to the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), before acting, individuals have beliefs about the results of their behaviour (behaviour beliefs), which then determine their decision to perform or not perform the action. The theory of compliance also explains that an individual's willingness to pay taxes is greatly influenced by psychological, social, and economic factors. The willingness to pay taxes is an important component in creating taxpayer compliance, whereby individuals consciously fulfil their obligations without coercion. Factors such as perceptions of fairness, trust in the government, and intrinsic motivation also have an influence. Attribution theory also explains that internal factors that encourage a person to behave compliantly or not in fulfilling their tax obligations are influenced by perceived internal factors.

Willpower is related to a person's intention to do something when they understand the benefits of that action. If someone understands that tax is an obligation that must be fulfilled, then they will intend and be willing to pay tax, or in other words, intend to fulfil their obligations. Conversely, if they do not fulfil their obligations, they will understand that there are sanctions from the state, so the existence of sanctions will also encourage the intention and will to fulfil their obligations.

The concept of willingness to pay tax is defined as the amount that a person is willing to contribute (in accordance with regulations) to finance public expenditure without receiving any direct services in return (Widayati & Nurlis, 2010). Thus, if a person understands their obligations, they will be willing to fulfil them. Research by Yoga & Dewi (2021) shows that awareness (in this case meaning willingness) has a positive and significant influence on the fulfilment of individual taxpayer obligations. Diah & Ode (2019) also found that awareness has a significant effect on taxpayer compliance. The theory of awareness quoted by (Irwan., 2011) explains that one meaning of awareness is realisation, a state of knowing or understanding, so it can be interpreted that a person will

have the willingness to pay taxes if they understand and are aware of the benefits of paying taxes.

(Azizah et al., 2016) examined the factors that influence the willingness to pay taxes among self-employed taxpayers. Tax willingness indicates an attitude towards the tax system in which tax motivation is described as an intrinsic motivation to pay taxes immediately (Alasfour et al., 2016). Tax motivation also fulfils the civic obligation to pay the correct amount of tax on time because paying tax is a national obligation. This can be interpreted as willingness arising from a person's intention to do something when they understand the benefits and penalties of doing so. The more one understands the benefits of taxes, the more one will intend to fulfil one's obligations, and the more one understands that taxes are an obligation that must be fulfilled without coercion, the more one will fulfil one's tax obligations. Thus, willingness is thought to influence the fulfilment of taxpayer obligations. Therefore, the research hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H₂: Willingness to pay taxes has a positive effect on the fulfilment of individual taxpayer obligations.

The Effect of Tax Office Service Quality on the Fulfilment of Individual Taxpayer Obligations

Attribution theory explains that individuals tend to seek causes behind events or actions, whether internal or external factors. In the context of taxation, when taxpayers interact with the Tax Office, the quality of service they receive will form the basis for their attribution. High-quality service that taxpayers perceive as proactive efforts and support from tax officials can lead to positive external attribution. This means that taxpayers may attribute the ease or smoothness of fulfilling their tax obligations to the efficiency and attentiveness of the tax office's services.

Furthermore, the SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman et al., 1988) identifies five main dimensions of service quality: Tangibles (physical evidence such as facilities and staff appearance), Reliability (consistent and accurate service reliability), Responsiveness (responsiveness and speed in assisting taxpayers), Assurance (assurance through staff knowledge and courtesy), and Empathy (personal attention to taxpayer needs). If the Tax Office is able to meet or exceed the expectations of individual taxpayers in these five dimensions, this positive experience will be internalised and perceived as a real commitment by the Tax Office to support the fulfilment of tax obligations, which in turn encourages taxpayer compliance.

Tax officials are expected to be cooperative, fair, honest, informative, helpful, and reliable in order to assist taxpayers in fulfilling their tax obligations. The quality of tax officials is also important to emphasise; tax offices are expected to have high motivation and competence in terms of expertise, knowledge, and experience in tax policy, tax administration, and tax legislation. The results of research by (Azizah et al., 2016) show that service has a positive effect on taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations. (Wilda., 2015) and (Ramadhanty & Zulaikha., 2020) also revealed that tax office services have a positive and significant effect on taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations. Based on the above, the following hypothesis can be drawn:

H3: The quality of tax office services has a positive effect on the fulfilment of individual taxpayer obligations.

The Effect of Tax Penalties on the Fulfilment of Individual Taxpayer Obligations.

Tax penalties serve to regulate taxpayers in fulfilling their tax obligations, both in terms of payment and reporting, in a timely manner and in accordance with applicable regulations. These sanctions are related to the attribution theory, whereby tax sanctions are external factors that influence taxpayers' perceptions of tax compliance. The perception that is formed is that violations or delinquency will harm taxpayers because they will have to accept sanctions, both administrative and criminal.

The theory of awareness explains that taxpayers' level of awareness of strict sanctions and legal consequences increases their understanding of the importance of fulfilling their tax obligations. This awareness motivates taxpayers to avoid the risks and negative impacts of non-compliance. Within the framework of tax compliance theory, sanctions are viewed as an effective control instrument which, if applied consistently and fairly, can instil fear of the consequences of violations, thereby encouraging increased compliance by taxpayers in fulfilling their tax obligations.

Research by Yoga & Dewi (2021) and Jatmiko (2006) shows that tax penalties have a positive and significant effect on taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations. Based on these findings, the research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H4: Tax penalties have a positive effect on the fulfilment of individual taxpayer obligations.

The Role of Tax Consultants in Moderating the Influence of Understanding Tax Regulations on the Fulfilment of Individual Taxpayer Obligations

In the Theory of Planned Behaviour, a person's behaviour is determined by their intentions, which are influenced by external factors (normative beliefs), thereby affecting their behaviour. Taxpayers' understanding of tax regulations is a process undertaken by taxpayers to learn about tax rules and apply them to fulfil their tax obligations. Understanding the important role of taxation in national development gives taxpayers confidence about the results they will obtain after paying taxes, namely a tangible contribution to development in their region.

Tax consultants play an important role in Indonesia's taxation system, which adopts a self-assessment system. Based on Minister of Finance Regulation No. 111/PMK.03/2014 as amended by PMK 175/PMK.01/2022, a tax consultant is a person who provides tax consulting services to taxpayers in order to exercise their rights and fulfil their tax obligations in accordance with tax laws and regulations. A. Nugraheni et al. (2021) state that tax consultants have a dual role as agents of the government and agents of taxpayers as their clients. Tax consultants are obliged to provide services to clients in accordance with tax laws. In addition, tax consultants also play a role in disseminating new tax provisions or changes and their implications for taxpayers (Darussalam et al., 2024).

Furthermore, tax consultants also play a role in guiding and encouraging taxpayers to fulfil their tax obligations in accordance with applicable tax regulations. Therefore, the role of tax consultants is thought to moderate the influence of understanding tax regulations on the fulfilment of individual taxpayers' tax obligations. Based on the above explanation, the following hypothesis can be proposed:

H₅: The Role of Tax Consultants in Moderating the Influence of Tax Regulation Understanding on the Fulfilment of Individual Taxpayer Obligations

The Role of Tax Consultants in Moderating the Influence of Tax Payment Willingness on the Fulfilment of Individual Taxpayer Obligations

Compliance theory explains that taxpayers' fulfilment of their tax obligations is influenced by both internal and external factors. The role of tax consultants as facilitators can moderate the relationship between willingness to pay taxes and fulfilment of tax obligations. Tax consultants help increase the effectiveness of willingness to pay into concrete actions by providing technical support and understanding of taxation mechanisms, thereby increasing the level of taxpayer compliance. In addition, for taxpayers with less than optimal willingness to pay, tax consultants act as strategic interventions that reduce normative barriers and compliance burdens, facilitating the shift from willingness to tax compliance.

The role of tax consultants is very strategic in providing professional advice and convincing taxpayers of the benefits of paying taxes. Based on Attribution Theory, a person's behaviour is influenced by their interpretation of the causes or reasons for an event, whether these originate from internal or external factors. Tax consultants, as an external factor, can influence the behaviour of taxpayers in complying with their tax obligations. Therefore, the role of tax consultants has the potential to moderate the influence of taxpayers' willingness to pay on the fulfilment of their tax obligations. Based on the above, the following hypothesis can be proposed:

H₆: The Role of Tax Consultants in Moderating the Influence of Taxpayer Willingness on the Fulfillment of Individual Taxpayer Obligations

The Role of Tax Consultants in Moderating the Influence of Tax Office Service Quality on the Fulfilment of Individual Taxpayer Obligations

Based on attribution theory, taxpayers seek to understand the causes behind the quality of service they receive from the tax office. If the service is considered high quality, for example, responsive officers, efficient systems, and clear information in accordance with the SERVQUAL dimensions of A. P. Parasuraman et al. (1988), taxpayers tend to attribute this to internal factors such as the Tax Office's commitment to excellent service. This internal attribution enhances positive perceptions of the taxation system and encourages taxpayers to fulfil their tax obligations. Conversely, poor service quality can be attributed to external factors that reduce taxpayers' motivation to fulfil their tax obligations.

Tax consultants with practical experience can provide advice or input related to taxation policies to taxpayers in order to comply with their tax obligations. In turn, optimising compliance will assist the tax authorities in increasing overall tax revenue. Therefore, the role of tax consultants can moderate the influence of the quality of tax office services on the fulfilment of tax obligations. Based on the above, the following hypothesis can be proposed:

H7: The Role of Tax Consultants in Moderating the Influence of Tax Office Service Quality on the Fulfilment of Individual Taxpayer Obligations

The Role of Tax Consultants in Moderating the Impact of Tax Penalties on the Fulfilment of Individual Taxpayer Obligations

Within the framework of attribution theory, taxpayers attribute the fulfilment of their tax obligations to their internal understanding of tax regulations. However, tax consultants act as moderators that influence this attribution process. For taxpayers with low understanding, tax consultants act as a credible external source, shifting the attribution of non-compliance from regulatory complexity to acquired skills through professional assistance, thereby increasing taxpayers' control over their tax obligations. Conversely, for taxpayers with a high level of understanding, tax consultants provide validation and reinforcement, strengthening internal attribution and supporting the optimisation of tax compliance. Thus, tax consultants moderate the influence of tax penalties on taxpayer compliance by reducing negative attribution barriers and strengthening positive attribution.

Tax consultants, with their professional expertise, assist taxpayers in complying with their tax obligations by providing advice that prevents penalties for non-compliance. In addition, tax consultants play a role in disseminating information related to new tax regulations and changes, along with their implications for taxpayers. With their practical experience, tax consultants not only bridge communication between taxpayers and tax authorities but also provide strategic input regarding tax policy. Therefore, tax consultants have a significant influence on taxpayer compliance (Darussalam et al., 2024). Based on this description, the hypothesis proposed is as follows:

H8: The Role of Tax Consultants in Moderating the Impact of Tax Sanctions on the Fulfilment of Individual Taxpayer Obligations

Research Methodology

This study is an associative study with a causal approach that aims to examine the causal relationship between independent variables, namely understanding of tax regulations (X1), willingness to pay taxes (X2), quality of tax office services (X3), and tax penalties (X4) on the fulfilment of individual taxpayer obligations as dependent variables (Y), as well as the role of tax consultants as moderating variables (Z) (Sugiyono, 2014). The research was conducted at the West Mataram Tax Office located at Langko Street Number. 74, Pejeruk, Ampenan District, Mataram City, West Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia. The population in this study consisted of all taxpayers registered at the West Mataram Tax Office, amounting to 148,697 taxpayers. Due to the large population size,

the sample was determined using non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling approach, where the sample determination technique was based on specific considerations (Sugiyono, 2014: 138). The sources selected based on the established criteria were registered and active Individual Taxpayers, Individual Taxpayers residing or conducting business activities in the administrative area of the West Mataram Tax Office, and individual taxpayer who were willing to be respondents and fill out the questionnaire completely and correctly.

This study utilised primary data collected through a survey using a questionnaire instrument. The questionnaire contained written questions answered by respondents to measure taxpayers' attitudes, opinions, and perceptions regarding the fulfilment of tax obligations (Sugiyono, 2014). The measurement used a Likert scale, which is an ordinal scale that assigns a value to each answer: 4 = Strongly Agree, 3 = Agree, 2 = Disagree, and 1 = Strongly Disagree. The collected data was then processed quantitatively based on the respondents' answer scores.

Research results

Description of Respondent Response Assessment

Tabulation and percentage calculations were performed for each statement item submitted for each variable to analyze the respondents' responses and provide an overview of the respondents' responses to each indicator of each variable. Furthermore, in the descriptive analysis, the average scores for the respondents' responses were also categorized to facilitate analysis. From this analysis, it can be concluded that:

$$\text{Class Interval} = \frac{\text{Maximum Value} - \text{Minimum value}}{\text{Total Class}}$$

In this study, the highest score was 4 (four), and the lowest score was 1. Both came from the questionnaire scale. The formula above produces the following class intervals:

$$\text{Class Interval} = \frac{4 - 1}{4} = 0.75$$

Tabel 2. Kategori Interval Kelas

No	Interval	Category
1	1,00 – 1,75	Very Low
2	1,76 – 2,50	Low
3	2,51 – 3,25	High
4	3,26 – 4,00	Very High

Description of Respondents' Answer Assessment on the Understanding of Tax Regulations Variable

Table 3. Respondents' Answers to the Understanding of Tax Regulations Variable

No	Items	Total Percentage of Answers								Total		Average
		1		2		3		4		Tot	%	
		Tot	%	Tot	%	Tot	%	Tot	%			
1	X1.1	1	1%	3	3%	37	37%	59	59%	100	100%	3,54
2	X1.2	2	2%	7	7%	62	62%	30	30%	100	100%	3,22
3	X1.3	1	1%	7	7%	62	62%	30	30%	100	100%	3,21
4	X1.4	2	2%	1	1%	72	72%	25	25%	100	100%	3,20
5	X1.5	3	3%	5	5%	60	60%	32	32%	100	100%	3,21
6	X1.6	2	2%	7	7%	62	62%	29	29%	100	100%	3,18
7	X1.7	3	3%	1	1%	62	62%	34	34%	100	100%	3,27
8	X1.8	2	2%	4	4%	72	72%	22	22%	100	100%	3,14
9	X1.9	3	3%	11	11%	58	58%	28	28%	100	100%	3,11
Total												3,23

The table 3 shows that the variable for understanding tax regulations has an average value of 3.23, or in the high category. This indicates that the overall level of understanding of tax regulations by individual taxpayers registered in the West Mataram Pratama Tax Office (KPP Pratama) area shows a positive response or agreement with each statement item.

Furthermore, as the data examination shows, respondents (Taxpayers) are highly aware of taxation, which is considered a citizen's responsibility to fulfill their obligations. The fact that taxpayers understand their basic obligations in carrying out their tax obligations is confirmed by the highest average score on statement item X1.1, which is 3.54, and the proportion of respondents who chose the Strongly Agree category of 59%. In addition, statements X1.2 and X1.3 relating to understanding the substance of tax regulations and understanding the current tax collection system, each received high average scores, each above 3.2.

Description of Respondents' Response Assessment on the Willingness to Pay Taxes Variable

Individual taxpayers' tax willingness to pay is generally quite high, as shown by the table of respondents' responses to the tax willingness variable above. The overall average score, 3.27, indicates a strong intention and desire to fulfill their tax obligations. This indicates that the majority of respondents agree to pay taxes in accordance with statutory provisions without having to wait for a tax assessment letter, as indicated by statement item X2.1, which obtained an average score of 3.16. The majority of respondents, or 64 percent, chose the Agree category. This condition indicates that taxpayers are acting proactively in fulfilling their tax obligations.

Table 4. Respondents' answers to the variable of willingness to pay taxes

No	Items	Total Percentage of Answers								Total		Average
		1		2		3		4		Tot	%	
		Tot	%	Tot	%	Tot	%	Tot	%			
1	X2.1	2	2%	7	7%	64	64%	27	27%	100	100%	3,16
2	X2.2	1	1%	11	11%	57	57%	31	31%	100	100%	3,18
3	X2.3	1	1%	4	4%	55	55%	40	40%	100	100%	3,34
4	X2.4	1	1%	4	4%	56	56%	39	39%	100	100%	3,33
5	X2.5	2	2%	1	1%	59	59%	38	38%	100	100%	3,33
6	X2.6	1	1%	2	2%	61	61%	36	36%	100	100%	3,32
7	X2.7	2	2%	5	5%	60	60%	33	33%	100	100%	3,24
Total												3,27

In statements X2.2 to X2.5, which cover the tax payment administration process such as providing STP and SKP documents, consulting before payment, and seeking information on payment procedures and locations, respondents gave positive assessment answers with a fairly high average score in the range of 3.18 to 3.34. Item X2.3, which covers consultation with parties who understand tax regulations, received the highest score of 3.34, indicating that respondents showed high awareness.

Description of Respondents' Response Assessment on the Tax Office Service Quality Variable

Table 5. Description of Respondents' Answers to the Tax Office Service Quality

No	Items	Total Percentage of Answers								Total		Average
		1		2		3		4		Tot	%	
		Tot	%	Tot	%	Tot	%	Tot	%			
1	X3.1	3	3%	4	4%	57	57%	36	36%	100	100%	3,26
2	X3.2	1	1%	4	4%	51	51%	44	44%	100	100%	3,38
3	X3.3	1	1%	7	7%	55	55%	37	37%	100	100%	3,28
4	X3.4	1	1%	7	7%	57	57%	35	35%	100	100%	3,26
5	X3.5	1	1%	11	11%	58	58%	30	30%	100	100%	3,17
6	X3.6	1	1%	2	2%	65	65%	32	32%	100	100%	3,28
7	X3.7	1	1%	4	4%	62	62%	33	33%	100	100%	3,27
8	X3.8	1	1%	3	3%	54	54%	42	42%	100	100%	3,37
9	X3.9	3	3%	14	14%	53	53%	30	30%	100	100%	3,10
10	X3.10	3	3%	17	17%	48	48%	32	32%	100	100%	3,09
11	X3.11	1	1%	10	10%	59	59%	30	30%	100	100%	3,18
Total												3,24

The table 5 shows that taxpayers' perceptions of service quality at the tax office were generally quite positive, with an overall average score of 3.24. This indicates that the majority of respondents rated the ease and convenience of the services provided between Agree and Strongly Agree. Item X3.2, which received the highest score of 3.38, assessed the friendly and welcoming attitude of the staff.

Description of Respondents' Answer Assessment on Tax Penalties Variables

Table 6. Respondents' Answers to the Tax Sanctions Variable

No	Items	Total Percentage of Answers								Total		Average
		1		2		3		4		Tot	%	
		Tot	%	Tot	%	Tot	%	Tot	%			
1	X4.1	5	5%	11	11%	63	63%	21	21%	100	100%	3,00
2	X4.2	7	7%	13	13%	57	57%	23	23%	100	100%	2,96
3	X4.3	4	4%	11	11%	59	59%	26	26%	100	100%	3,07
4	X4.4	4	4%	15	15%	54	54%	27	27%	100	100%	3,04
5	X4.5	5	5%	13	13%	63	63%	19	19%	100	100%	2,96
6	X4.6	6	6%	17	17%	58	58%	19	19%	100	100%	2,90
Total												2,99

Table 6 shows that respondents' perceptions of tax sanctions are generally high. This is reflected in the average overall score of 2.99, which falls within the 2.51–3.25 range, indicating a high level of agreement or awareness among taxpayers regarding the existence and implications of tax sanctions.

Each item in the X4.1 to X4.6 tax sanctions variable consistently shows an average individual score ranging from 2.90 to 3.07. This underscores that the majority of respondents have a deep understanding of the consequences of violating tax obligations, whether in the form of administrative fines, criminal charges, or other sanctions stipulated by applicable tax regulations.

This high average score indirectly reflects a tendency toward negative perceptions among taxpayers toward tax sanctions. Awareness of the potential losses, both financial and reputational, resulting from the imposition of sanctions creates feelings of discomfort or even objection. In other words, these results indicate that taxpayers perceive strict tax sanctions as detrimental if they violate the provisions. This can encourage greater compliance, but it also indicates that sanctions are viewed as a burden or consequence to be avoided whenever possible, reflecting a strong disincentive resulting from their implementation within the tax system.

Description of Respondents' Answer Assessment on the Tax Consultant Role Variable

The average overall score for this variable reached 3.59, indicating a very high level of agreement among respondents regarding the role of tax consultants. This score falls into the Very High category, indicating that tax consultants play a significant role as mediators who assist taxpayers in effectively fulfilling their tax obligations.

Each statement item showed positive consistency, with the average item score ranging from 3.47 to 3.65. For example, item Z1, which states "The tax consultant provided clear information regarding my tax obligations," received the highest average score of 3.65, indicating that the majority of respondents highly appreciated the information provided by the tax consultant. Other statement items also received high positive responses,

including assistance in filing and reporting taxes and updates on information related to tax regulations, each of which received an average score approaching 3.6.

Table 7. Respondents' Answers to the Tax Consultant Role Variable

No	Items	Total Percentage of Answers								Total		Average
		1		2		3		4		Tot	%	
		Tot	%	Tot	%	Tot	%	Tot	%			
1	Z1	1	1%	0	0%	32	32%	67	67%	100	100%	3,65
2	Z2	1	1%	0	0%	35	35%	64	64%	100	100%	3,62
3	Z3	1	1%	2	2%	46	46%	51	51%	100	100%	3,47
4	Z4	1	1%	1	1%	31	31%	67	67%	100	100%	3,64
5	Z5	2	2%	0	0%	33	33%	65	65%	100	100%	3,61
6	Z6	2	2%	0	0%	36	36%	62	62%	100	100%	3,58
7	Z7	2	2%	0	0%	35	35%	63	63%	100	100%	3,59
8	Z8	2	2%	0	0%	47	47%	51	51%	100	100%	3,47
9	Z9	1	1%	1	1%	36	36%	62	62%	100	100%	3,59
10	Z10	1	1%	1	1%	35	35%	63	63%	100	100%	3,6
11	Z11	1	1%	1	1%	30	30%	68	68%	100	100%	3,65
12	Z12	1	1%	1	1%	33	33%	65	65%	100	100%	3,62
Total											3,59	

Each statement item in Table 7 showed positive consistency, with the average item score ranging from 3.47 to 3.65. For example, item Z1, which states "The tax consultant provided clear information regarding my tax obligations," received the highest average score of 3.65, indicating that the majority of respondents highly appreciated the information provided by the tax consultant. Other statement items also received high positive responses, including assistance in filing and reporting taxes and updates on information related to tax regulations, each of which received an average score approaching 3.6.

These results demonstrate that tax consultants serve not only as technical service providers but also as strategic partners capable of building trust and increasing taxpayer comfort in fulfilling their tax administration obligations. This role is crucial in promoting better compliance and ensuring that taxpayers receive up-to-date information and adequate support in fulfilling their tax obligations in accordance with applicable tax regulations.

Description of Respondents' Answer Assessment on the Tax Obligation Fulfillment Variable

The table of respondents' answers in the survey results obtained above shows that the average score for the overall variable of fulfillment of tax obligations (Y) was 3.32, which falls into the Very High category on the indicator scale used (range 3.26 - 4.00). This indicates that respondents generally have a high level of compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations.

Tabel 8. Respondents' Answers to the Tax Obligation Fulfillment Variable

No	Items	Total Percentage of Answers								Total		Average
		1		2		3		4				
		Tot	%	Tot	%	Tot	%	Tot	%	Tot	%	
1	Y1	2	2%	2	2%	54	54%	42	42%	100	100%	3,36
2	Y2	1	1%	4	4%	56	56%	39	39%	100	100%	3,33
3	Y3	1	1%	2	2%	63	63%	34	34%	100	100%	3,3
4	Y4	1	1%	3	3%	60	60%	36	36%	100	100%	3,31
5	Y5	1	1%	3	3%	60	60%	36	36%	100	100%	3,31
6	Y6	2	2%	1	1%	61	61%	36	36%	100	100%	3,31
Total											3,32	

For each statement item in Table 8, the level of respondent agreement (answers "Agree" and "Strongly Agree") was predominantly in the range of 90% and above. For example, in item Y1 regarding the obligation to register with the tax office, 54% of respondents answered agree and 42% strongly agreed, with an average score of 3.36. Similarly, in item Y2 regarding the timely completion and submission of tax returns, the average score reached 3.33. Furthermore, items Y3, Y4, Y5, and Y6 also showed a similar pattern with average scores ranging from 3.30 to 3.36. This indicates that taxpayers tend to consistently comply with their tax obligations.

Data Quality Test Results

Validity Test Results

Validity testing is used to measure the validity of a questionnaire. This validity test uses the Pearson correlation approach, with the stipulation that if the indicator has a significance value below $\alpha = 0.05$ and the value of Pearson correlation $\geq r$ table (0.1946) and is positive, then the statement item is considered valid, and vice versa. The results of the validity test for all question items in the 6 proposed variables are presented in the table below:

Tabel 9. Results of the Validity Test of the Tax Regulation Understanding Instrument

No	Item	Pearson Correlation	Sig (0,05)	Remarks
1	X1.1	,643**	< 0,001	Valid
2	X1.2	,745**	< 0,001	Valid
3	X1.3	,777**	< 0,001	Valid
4	X1.4	,749**	< 0,001	Valid
5	X1.5	,779**	< 0,001	Valid
6	X1.6	,787**	< 0,001	Valid
7	X1.7	,725**	< 0,001	Valid
8	X1.8	,853**	< 0,001	Valid
9	X1.9	,809**	< 0,001	Valid

From the results of Table 9, it can be seen that all statement items for variables that have a sub-variable of understanding tax regulations are at a significance level below 0.05 and the Pearson correlation value is $> r$ table (0.1946) and is positive. Therefore, it can be concluded that the statements in this research variable are valid. This means that all statement items used in this study are able to express something measured in the questionnaire.

Table 10. Results of the Validity Test of the Willingness to Pay Tax Instrument

No	Item	Pearson Correlation	Sig (0,05)	Remarks
1	X2.1	0771**	< 0,001	Valid
2	X2.2	,704**	< 0,001	Valid
3	X2.3	,741**	< 0,001	Valid
4	X2.4	,814**	< 0,001	Valid
5	X2.5	,814**	< 0,001	Valid
6	X2.6	,755**	< 0,001	Valid
7	X2.7	,791**	< 0,001	Valid

The test results in Table 10 show that all statement items for the willingness to pay taxes variable are at a significance level below $\alpha = 0.05$ and the pearson correlation $> r$ table (0.1946) and is positive, so it can be concluded that the statement items used in this study are valid. This means that all statement items used in this study are able to express something that is measured in the research questionnaire.

Table 11. Results of the Validity Test of the Tax Office Service Quality Instrument

No	Item	Pearson Correlation	Sig (0,05)	Remarks
1	X3.1	,822**	0,000	Valid
2	X3.2	,827**	0,000	Valid
3	X3.3	,842**	0,000	Valid
4	X3.4	,855**	0,000	Valid
5	X3.5	,851**	0,000	Valid
6	X3.6	,830**	0,000	Valid
7	X3.7	,810**	0,000	Valid
8	X3.8	,701**	0,000	Valid
9	X3.9	,834**	0,000	Valid
10	X3.10	,815**	0,000	Valid
11	X3.11	,817**	0,000	Valid

Table 11 shows that all statement items for variables that have sub-variables of tax office service quality are also at a significance level below $\alpha = 0.05$ and the pearson correlation $> r$ table (0.1946) and has a positive value. Therefore, it can be concluded that the statements in this study are valid. This means that all statement items used in this study are able to express something measured in the questionnaire.

Table 12. Results of the Validity Test of Tax Sanction Instruments

No	Item	Pearson Correlation	Sig (0,05)	Remarks
1	X4.1	,834**	< 0,001	Valid
2	X4.2	,872**	< 0,001	Valid
3	X4.3	,824**	< 0,001	Valid
4	X4.4	,839**	< 0,001	Valid
5	X4.5	,895**	< 0,001	Valid
6	X4.6	,865**	< 0,001	Valid

From Table 12, it can be seen that all statement items for variables that have sub-variables of tax sanctions are also at a significance level below $\alpha = 0.05$ and the pearson correlation $> r$ table (0.1946) and is positive, so it can be concluded that the statements in this study are valid. This means that all statement items used in this study are able to express something measured in the questionnaire.

Table 13. Results of the Validity Test of the Tax Consultant Role Instrument

No	Item	Pearson Correlation	Sig (0,05)	Remarks
1	Z.1	,794**	0,000	Valid
2	Z.2	,816**	0,000	Valid
3	Z.3	,761**	0,000	Valid
4	Z.4	,834**	0,000	Valid
5	Z.5	,813**	0,000	Valid
6	Z.6	,845**	0,000	Valid
7	Z.7	,858**	0,000	Valid
8	Z.8	,787**	0,000	Valid
9	Z.9	,870**	0,000	Valid
10	Z.10	,838**	0,000	Valid
11	Z.11	,885**	0,000	Valid
12	Z.12	,809**	0,000	Valid

Table 13 shows that all statement items for the tax consultant role variable are also at a significance level below $\alpha = 0.05$ and the pearson correlation $> r$ table (0.1946) and has a positive value. Therefore, it can be concluded that the statements in this study are valid. Therefore, it can be said that all statement items used in the questionnaire are valid for measuring the research variables, so it can be continued to the reliability testing stage.

Table 14. Results of the Validity Test of Tax Obligation Fulfillment Instruments

No	Item	Pearson Correlation	Sig (0,05)	Remarks
1	Y.1	,760**	< 0,001	Valid
2	Y.2	,818**	< 0,001	Valid
3	Y.3	,812**	< 0,001	Valid
4	Y.4	,807**	< 0,001	Valid
5	Y.5	,861**	< 0,001	Valid
6	Y.6	,807**	< 0,001	Valid

The results of the validity test in Table 14 show that all statement items for variables that have sub-variables of fulfilling tax obligations are also at a significance level below $\alpha = 0.05$ and the pearson correlation $> r$ -table (0.1946) and have a positive value, so it can be concluded that the statements in this study are valid.

Reliability Test Results

The reliability test in this study aims to assess the extent to which the measuring instrument used in this study is reliable or trustworthy. According to Ghozali (2005:41), the reliability of a variable construct is said to be good if it has a Cronbach Alpha value ≥ 0.7 and conversely, if the Cronbach Alpha < 0.7 then a construct is said to be bad or there is no reliability.

Table 15. Reliability Test Results

No	Variable	Cronbach alpha	N of Item	Remarks
1	Understanding Tax Regulations (X1)	0,909	9	Reliable
2	Willingness to Pay Taxes (X2)	0,885	7	Reliable
3	Quality of Tax Office Services (X3)	0,950	11	Reliable
4	Tax Penalties (X4)	0,926	6	Reliable
5	Role of Tax Consultants (Z)	0,957	12	Reliable
6	Understanding Tax Regulations (X1)	0,895	6	Reliable

The reliability test results in Table 15 show that the Cronbach's alpha value for the variables understanding tax regulations, willingness to pay taxes, quality of tax office services, tax sanctions, the role of tax consultants, and fulfillment of tax obligations has a value of more than 0.7. Thus, according to the Cronbach's alpha calculation results, all indicators measuring all proposed variables are declared reliable.

Classical Assumption Test

Normality Test

Table 16. Normality Test

Description	Unstandardized Residual
N (sampel)	100
Kolmogorof Smirnov (K-S)	0,080
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)c	0,112

Based on the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) normality test in Table 16, a statistical value of 0.080 with a significance of 0.112 was obtained. Since the significance value is > 0.05 , the residual data is normally distributed. Thus, the assumption of normality in regression analysis is fulfilled, and the analysis results can be considered valid.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 17. Multicollinearity Test

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		
Understanding Tax Regulations (X1)	0,299	3,340
Willingness to Pay Taxes (X2)	0,282	3,545
Quality of Tax Office Services (X3)	0,377	2,651
Tax Penalties (X4)	0,714	1,401
Role of Tax Consultants (Z)	0,693	1,443

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test in Table 17, the tolerance value is close to 1 and the VIF is around 2 for each variable. Understanding of tax regulations has a tolerance of 0.299 and a VIF of 3.340; willingness to pay taxes has a tolerance of 0.282 and a VIF of 3.545; the quality of tax office services has a tolerance of 0.377 and a VIF of 2.651; tax penalties have a tolerance of 0.714 and a VIF of 1.401; and the role of tax consultants has a tolerance of 0.693 and a VIF of 1.443. Tolerance values > 0.10 and VIF < 10 indicate that there are no multicollinearity issues in the regression model.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 18. Heteroscedasticity Test

Model	Sig
Constant	0,140
Understanding Tax Regulations (X1)	0,504
Willingness to Pay Taxes (X2)	0,609
Quality of Tax Office Services (X3)	0,186
Tax Penalties (X4)	0,075
Role of Tax Consultants (Z)	0,764

Based on Table 18, all independent variables have a significance value > 0.05 , indicating no heteroscedasticity issues in the regression model. Thus, the model is considered valid for predicting tax compliance by individual taxpayer.

Hypothesis Test Results

Multiple Linear Regression Test

Table 19. Multiple Regression Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	0,228	0,211		1,078	0,284
Understanding Tax Regulations (X1)	0,223	0,092	0,228	2,427	0,017

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error			
Willingness to Pay Taxes (X2)	0,496	0,098	0,494	5,058	< 0,001
Quality of Tax Office Services (X3)	-0,119	0,075	-0,133	-1,582	0,117
Tax Penalties (X4)	0,238	0,046	0,319	5,187	< 0,001
Role of Tax Consultants (Z)	0,118	0,062	0,117	1,889	0,062

a. Understanding of Tax Regulations Variable

The regression coefficient of the tax regulation understanding variable (X1) is 0.223 with a significance value of 0.017 (< 0.05), indicating a positive and significant effect on tax compliance (Y). This means that every one-unit increase in understanding of tax regulations will increase tax compliance by 0.223 units, assuming other variables remain constant.

b. Willingness to Pay Taxes Variable

The regression coefficient of the willingness to pay tax variable (X2) is 0.496 with a significance of < 0.001 (< 0.05), indicating a positive and significant effect on tax compliance (Y). Each one-unit increase in willingness to pay taxes will increase tax compliance by 0.496, with other variables held constant.

c. Quality of Tax Office Services Variable

The regression coefficient for the tax office service quality variable (X3) is -0.119 with a significance of 0.117 (> 0.05), indicating an insignificant effect on tax compliance (Y). Although the negative coefficient indicates an empirical tendency that an increase in service quality is associated with a decrease in compliance, statistically this effect is not proven. Thus, the hypothesis regarding the effect of tax office service quality on tax compliance is rejected.

d. Tax Penalties Variable

The regression coefficient of the tax penalty variable (X4) of 0.238 with a significance of < 0.001 (< 0.05) indicates a positive and significant effect on tax compliance (Y). Each one-unit increase in tax penalties will increase tax compliance by 0.238, with other variables held constant. Thus, an increase in tax penalties is associated with an increase in the level of tax compliance.

e. The Role of Tax Consultants Variable

The regression coefficient Z is 0.118 with a significance value (Sig.) of 0.062, which is close to significance at the 0.05 level but is still conventionally considered insignificant if the limit is 0.05. This indicates that the role of tax consultants (Z) does not have a significant effect on tax compliance (Y).

Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) Test Result

Based on the regression results obtained, it is shown that independent variables such as understanding of tax regulations, willingness to pay taxes, quality of tax office services, tax sanctions, and the use of moderating variables such as the role of tax consultants were tested in a regression model together with interaction variables (interaction between independent variables and moderators) using the SPSS 27 programme. The following are the results of the Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) test:

Table 20. Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) Test Result

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	0,133	0,287		0,462	0,645
Understanding of Tax Regulations (X1)	0,231	0,097	0,236	2,376	0,020
Willingness to Pay Taxes (X2)	0,509	0,101	0,507	5,059	< 0,001
Quality of Tax Office Services (X3)	-0,118	0,076	-0,132	-1,561	0,122
Tax Penalties (X4)	0,211	0,051	0,283	4,126	< 0,001
Role of Tax Consultants (Z)	0,147	0,075	0,146	1,956	0,054
X1*Z (Role of Tax Consultants)	-0,311	0,257	-0,386	-1,210	0,229
X2*Z (Role of Tax Consultants)	0,271	0,222	0,347	1,222	0,225
X3*Z (Role of Tax Consultants)	-0,098	0,201	-0,121	-0,487	0,628
X4*Z (Role of Tax Consultants)	0,121	0,141	0,145	0,861	0,392

Based on the statistical test results in Table 20, the following regression equation was obtained:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 Z + \beta_6 + (X_1 \times Z) + \beta_7 + (X_2 \times Z) + \beta_8 + (X_3 \times Z) + \beta_9 + (X_4 \times Z) + \varepsilon$$

$$Y = (0,133) + (0,231) + (0,509) + (-0,118) + (0,211) + (0,147) + (-0,311) + (0,271) + (-0,098) + (0,121)$$

a. Understanding Tax Regulations Variable

The regression coefficient for the variable of understanding of taxation regulations (β_1) is 0.231, which is positive, with a p-value of $0.020 < (0.05)$, indicating that the better

the understanding of taxation regulations, the higher the fulfilment of taxation obligations significantly. This means that the hypothesis stating that there is a positive influence is accepted.

f. Willingness to Pay Taxes Variable

The regression coefficient for the willingness to pay tax variable (β_2) of 0.509 and $p < 0.001$ has a positive and highly significant effect on tax compliance, meaning that if the willingness to pay tax increases, the level of tax compliance will also increase. This is the variable with the greatest effect (highest coefficient and very low p-value).

b. Quality of Tax Office Services Variable

The regression coefficient for the tax office service quality variable (β_3) is -0.118, which is negative with a p-value of $0.122 > 0.05$, meaning that the effect of the tax office service quality variable on the fulfilment of individual taxpayer obligations is not statistically significant. This negative coefficient indicates that there is an empirical tendency for an increase in tax office service quality to be associated with a decrease in tax compliance. Thus, it can be said that tax office service quality does not contribute significantly to tax compliance in this study. Therefore, the hypothesis regarding the influence of tax office service quality on tax compliance is not proven.

c. Tax Penalties Variable

The tax penalty variable has a regression coefficient of 0.211 with a p-value of less than 0.001, indicating a positive and highly significant effect on tax compliance. This illustrates that the more effective the application of tax penalties, the greater the motivation of taxpayers to fulfil their obligations. Furthermore, this regression equation also shows that if tax penalties increase, the level of tax compliance will also increase.

d. The Role of Tax Consultants Variable

The regression coefficient for the tax consultant variable is 0.147 with a p-value of 0.054, which is slightly above the significance threshold of 0.05, indicating that the role of tax consultants has a positive influence but is not statistically strong enough to be considered significant. In other words, the role of tax consultants makes a limited contribution to supporting the fulfilment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers.

e. Interaction Variables in Understanding Tax Regulations and the Role of Tax Consultants

The regression coefficient for the interaction variable of understanding tax regulations and the role of tax consultants is -0.311 with a p-value of $0.229 > 0.05$. This indicates that there is no strong statistical evidence that the role of tax consultants moderates the influence of understanding tax regulations on tax compliance.

f. Interaction Variables of Willingness to Pay Taxes and the Role of Tax Consultants

The regression coefficient for the interaction variable of willingness to pay taxes and the role of tax consultants is 0.271 with a p-value of $0.225 > 0.05$. This means that the role of tax consultants does not function as a significant moderating variable in strengthening or weakening the influence between willingness to pay taxes and fulfilment of tax obligations.

g. Interaction Variables of Tax Office Service Quality and the Role of Tax Consultants

The regression coefficient for the interaction variable of tax office service quality and the role of tax consultants is -0.098, and the p-value is $0.628 > 0.05$. This interaction variable shows that there is no significant moderating effect of the role of tax consultants on the influence of tax office service quality on tax compliance.

h. Interaction Variables of Tax Sanctions and the Role of Tax Consultants

The regression coefficient of the interaction variable between tax penalties and the role of tax consultants is 0.121 with a p-value of $0.392 > 0.05$, indicating that there is no significant moderating effect of the role of tax consultants on the effect of tax penalties on tax compliance.

Based on the results of multiple regression analysis (Table 17), the Tax Consultant Role (Z) variable does not have a significant effect on Tax Compliance with a significance value of 0.062 ($p > 0.05$). Furthermore, the results of the Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) (Table 18) show that all interaction variables between the role of tax consultants and other independent variables are also not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). The consistency of these findings indicates that the role of tax consultants does not play a significant role either as a direct predictor or as a moderating variable in influencing tax compliance. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no significant moderating effect in this model, so that the type of moderation that occurs is neutral or even no moderation at all.

Coefisiensi Determination (R^2) Test Result

The value of the coefficient of determination (R^2) serves to determine the percentage contribution of the independent variable and the moderating variable, together with the moderating interaction variable, simultaneously to the dependent variable. The R^2 value indicates the percentage of variation in the dependent variable; the coefficient values can be seen in Table 21.

Table 21. R Square Test Result / Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0,869	0,754	0,730	0,2485

Table 21, a coefficient (R) value of 0.869 was obtained, which means that the independent and moderating variables, as well as the moderating and dependent interaction variables, are indicated to have a very strong correlation between the variables. Furthermore, the R-squared value of 0.754 indicates that 75.4% of the variation in tax

compliance can be explained by this regression model through the independent variables included. This indicates that these factors have a significant and relevant contribution in influencing taxpayers in fulfilling their tax obligations.

The adjusted R-squared value of 0.730 represents a realistic value considering the number of variables and sample size of the study. This value still indicates a high level of model fit, approximately 73%, which means that the model remains robust when adjusted for the complexity of the data and variables.

These results also indicate that regression models incorporating independent variables such as understanding of tax regulations, willingness to pay taxes, quality of tax office services, tax penalties, and the role of tax consultants, together with moderating interaction variables ($X*Z$), are able to explain very well the factors that influence the fulfilment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers.

The coefficient of determination (R-squared) value of 75.4% is a strong indication that these variables are indeed relevant and significant in describing the level of tax compliance by individual taxpayers. This proves that the interaction between the moderating variable (the role of tax consultants) and other independent variables does not weaken the overall model fit. However, it should be noted that 24.6% of taxpayer behaviour variation cannot be explained by the model. This indicates that there are other influencing factors, such as macroeconomic conditions, taxpayer attitudes or perceptions, socio-cultural aspects, and possibly other external variables that require further study in subsequent research.

In practical terms, these results indicate that improved understanding of tax regulations, willingness to pay taxes, and enforcement of tax penalties, coupled with the role of tax consultants, can substantially increase taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations. Meanwhile, the quality of service provided by tax offices is known to have a negative and insignificant correlation with the fulfilment of tax obligations. This indicates that the quality of service provided by tax offices may not yet be a major driving factor in improving taxpayer compliance, or it may be related to taxpayers' perceptions of these services, which need to be further improved in order to have a positive impact. (Continue with the meaning of B negative – provide logical reasons based on SPSS figures, context, and theory.)

Results of the t-test hypothesis

Hypothesis 1 (H_1)

Based on the results of the Moderating Regression Analysis (MRA), it can be concluded that understanding of tax regulations has a t-value of 2.376 > t-table 1.984 with a significance probability of 0.020. A positive t-value indicates that the relationship between understanding of tax regulations (X_1) and compliance with tax obligations (Y) is in the same direction. The significance probability of 0.05 is smaller than the significance level. Thus, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and hypothesis 1 (H_1), which states that understanding tax regulations has a positive and significant effect, is accepted.

Hypothesis 2 (**H₂**)

The variable of willingness to pay taxes shows that the calculated t-value is 5.059, which will be compared with the t-table value in the study of 1.984. The calculated t-value in this hypothesis is greater than the table t-value. In addition, the p-value or significance level is $<0.001 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_2 is accepted, which means that there is a positive and significant effect of willingness to pay taxes on the fulfilment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers.

Hypothesis 3 (**H₃**)

The Tax Office Service Quality variable (X_3) is known to have a t-value of -1.561, which is smaller than the t-table value of 1.984 with a significance value of 0.122, meaning that it is not significant at the 5% level. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected, and H_3 , which states that the quality of tax office services has a positive and significant effect on tax compliance, is rejected. This result may be due to other perceptions of taxpayers regarding services that do not yet have a direct impact on compliance behaviour. The negative t-value also indicates an opposite or negative relationship between service quality and tax compliance in the context of this study.

Hypothesis 4 (**H₄**)

The Tax Penalty variable (X_4) shows a t-value of 4.126 $>$ t-table 1.984 with a significance of <0.001 , which is less than the significance level of 0.05, meaning that there is a positive and significant effect on the fulfilment of tax obligations. Thus, H_0 is rejected, and hypothesis 4 (H_4), which states that tax penalties have a positive and significant effect on the fulfilment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers, is accepted.

Hypothesis 5 (**H₅**)

Based on Table 18 above, the interaction coefficient value between understanding of tax regulations and the role of tax consultants is -0.311 with a t-value of -1.210 $<$ t-table 1.984 and a significance probability of 0.229 ($p > 0.05$). Thus, hypothesis 5 (H_5), which states that the role of tax consultants moderates the effect of understanding tax regulations on the fulfilment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers, is rejected. This indicates that the role of tax consultants does not significantly moderate the influence between understanding tax regulations and compliance with tax obligations. In other words, although understanding tax regulations has a positive effect, the existence of tax consultants does not strengthen or weaken this effect in the context of this sample population.

Hypothesis 6 (**H₆**)

The interaction test results show that the positive coefficient value is 0.271 with a t value of 1.222 $<$ t table 1.984 and a significance of 0.225 ($p > 0.05$). Thus, hypothesis 6 (H_6), which states that the role of tax consultants moderates the effect of willingness to pay taxes on the fulfilment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers, is rejected. This indicates that willingness to pay taxes has a direct positive and significant effect on the

fulfilment of tax obligations, but the role of tax consultants does not have a significant moderating effect on this influence.

Hypothesis 7 (H₇)

The interaction variable between the role of tax consultants and the quality of tax office services has an interaction coefficient value of -0.098 with a t-value of $-0.487 < t\text{-table } 1.984$ and a p-value of 0.628 ($p > 0.05$). Thus rejecting hypothesis 7 (H₇), which states that the role of tax consultants moderates the effect of tax office service quality on tax compliance. This means that the role of tax consultants does not play a significant role in moderating the effect between the perception of tax office service quality and tax compliance among individual taxpayers.

Hypothesis 8 (H₈)

The interaction variable between the role of tax consultants and tax sanctions shows an interaction coefficient value of 0.121, a t-value of $0.861 < t\text{ table } 1.984$, and a significance probability of 0.392 ($p > 0.05$), thus rejecting hypothesis 8 (H₈), which states that the role of tax consultants moderates the effect of tax sanctions on tax compliance. Although tax sanctions have a significant direct effect on tax compliance among individual taxpayers, the role of tax consultants neither strengthens nor weakens this effect in a moderating manner.

Discussion

This study aims to determine the effect of understanding tax regulations, willingness to pay taxes, quality of tax office services and tax penalties on tax compliance, with the role of tax consultants as a moderating variable.

The Effect of Understanding Tax Regulations on the Fulfilment of Tax Obligations

Based on the tests conducted, it can be concluded that understanding tax regulations has a positive and significant effect on the fulfilment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers. This can be seen from the t-value, which is greater than the t-table value, namely $2.376 > 1.984$, and a significance value of 0.020 ($p < 0.05$). These results indicate that individual taxpayers registered with the West Mataram Tax Office generally have a good understanding of tax regulations, which is then translated into the fulfilment of their tax obligations.

The results of this study also explain that with the formation of a good understanding of tax regulations, taxpayers will also develop compliant behaviour in fulfilling their tax obligations. This is also explained by Mangiwa & Asyik (2023), who state that the higher and more positive the level of taxpayers' understanding of tax regulations, the higher and more positive taxpayers will be in complying with these regulations and fulfilling their tax obligations.

In addition, the results of this study are also supported by the results of their research (Ramadhanty & Zulaikha, 2020), which examined the influence of understanding taxation, the quality of fiscal services, the tax transparency system, taxpayer awareness, and tax penalties on the compliance of individual taxpayers. Their research results indicate that understanding tax regulations has a positive and significant influence on fulfilling tax obligations. Further research was conducted by Kumala & Ayu (2021), who examined the influence of knowledge and understanding of tax regulations on the willingness of individual taxpayers to pay taxes, with positive and significant results. (Halimah et al. 2024), in their research, stated that understanding tax regulations has an influence on taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations.

Furthermore, this study is also in line with the Theory of Planned Behaviour, which places knowledge and attitude as determining factors of intention and behaviour, whereby a good understanding of tax regulations increases individuals' awareness of fulfilling their obligations correctly. Understanding tax regulations is one of the important factors that influence taxpayers' compliance with their tax obligations. In accordance with the Theory of Planned Behaviour, knowledge and attitudes formed from a good understanding of tax regulations become the basis for the formation of intentions and tax compliance behaviour. By thoroughly understanding tax policies and regulations, taxpayers tend to have a higher awareness of fulfilling their tax obligations correctly and on time.

Furthermore, Attribution Theory provides an additional explanatory framework regarding how taxpayers interpret and attribute the causes of their compliance behaviour. When taxpayers have a good understanding of taxation rules, they tend to attribute their tax compliance to positive internal factors, such as moral awareness and personal responsibility towards tax obligations. This kind of attribution increases intrinsic motivation, which is far more effective in ensuring consistent compliance behaviour than relying solely on external factors, such as the threat of sanctions or the influence of tax consultants.

Furthermore, according to awareness theory, understanding tax regulations plays a role in fostering taxpayers' awareness of the social norms and obligations inherent in the tax context. This heightened awareness of tax obligations implies a stronger commitment from taxpayers to fulfil their obligations consistently and responsibly. Those with a good understanding will not view tax regulations as merely a burden or administrative obligation but as part of their social contribution and legal responsibility.

The Effect of Willingness to Pay Taxes on Compliance with Tax Obligations

The test results show that willingness to pay taxes has a positive and significant effect on the fulfillment of individual taxpayers' tax obligations. This is indicated by the calculated t-value, which is greater than the t-table value, namely $5.059 > 1.984$, and a significance probability of <0.001 ($p < 0.05$). The results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Gusti et al. (2021) and (Neyla Safitri et al., 2025), which states that meaningful awareness and willingness of taxpayers have a significant effect on the fulfillment of tax obligations.

These results also indicate that the higher the taxpayer's willingness to pay taxes, the greater the fulfillment of tax obligations. This finding is in line with the Theory of Planned Behavior, where willingness or intention is the main determinant of a person's actual behavior. In the context of taxation, willingness to pay taxes is an expression of taxpayers' intentions that arises after going through a process of considering attitudes, social norms, and perceptions of control over the act of paying taxes. This means that taxpayers who have a positive attitude towards taxes, supported by subjective norms from their social environment, and who feel capable of fulfilling their obligations will tend to consistently execute their intention to pay taxes.

Furthermore, these results are also supported by the tabulation of questionnaire responses regarding respondents' willingness to pay taxes, with the majority of responses agreeing and strongly agreeing with the six indicators used to measure willingness to pay taxes, namely willingness to prepare the documents required for paying taxes, willingness to seek information on how, place, and deadline for tax payment, willingness to consult before paying taxes, willingness to pay taxes without relying on the existence of a tax assessment letter, willingness to set one's own schedule and pay on time, and willingness to allocate funds to pay taxes.

Overall, willingness to pay taxes can be understood as a key variable that acts as the main driver in fulfilling tax obligations, based on cross-theories, namely TPB, attribution theory, awareness theory, and compliance theory. This indicates that compliant behavior in fulfilling tax obligations is not merely a response to rules and sanctions but also the result of complex psychological and social processes in which intention and attribution play a central role.

The Effect of Tax Office Service Quality on Tax Compliance

The Tax Office Service Quality variable (X3) in this study shows a negative regression coefficient of -0.118 with a significance value of 0.122, indicating that statistically, the effect of service quality on tax compliance is insignificant. These results indicate that, although the quality of service at the tax office is considered good, it is not yet a major factor in encouraging taxpayers to fulfill their tax obligations. This can be understood as meaning that the quality of service at the tax office is not yet a stimulus that has a direct impact on the behavior of individual taxpayers in fulfilling their tax obligations.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by (Fauziah & Hidayat, 2022) and (Kumala & Ayu, 2021), which states that the quality of tax office services has no effect on the fulfillment of individual taxpayer obligations. Quality service is service that can satisfy taxpayers and remains within the limits of meeting accountable service standards and is carried out continuously. Good service quality is the result received by taxpayers and supported by personnel, in this case tax officers at the West Mataram Tax Office, which is measured by indicators of physical evidence, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

However, the results of this study contradict the expectation that the better the quality of service provided by the tax office, the easier it will be for taxpayers to fulfill their tax obligations. The results of this study indicate that, although no significant direct influence

was found, this does not necessarily mean that service quality is unimportant. It is possible that other factors, such as taxpayer characteristics, subjective perceptions, internal motivation, and other external factors that were not directly measured in this study, also influence the relationship between service and the fulfillment of individual taxpayer obligations.

Good service can indeed create a supportive environment and make it easier for taxpayers to fulfill their obligations, but if it is not accompanied by strong awareness and compliance, the influence of service alone may not be enough to encourage behavioral change. This is also in line with the theory of planned behavior and attribution theory, which state that individuals are more likely to fulfill their obligations if they internally recognize the importance of compliance, rather than simply because of adequate service from the tax office.

In addition, subjective factors such as taxpayers' perceptions of the credibility of tax officials, previous service experiences, and trust in the taxation system can also play an important role in influencing the extent to which service quality affects taxpayers' compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations. Both emotional and cognitive factors are often difficult to measure quantitatively but have a real impact on taxpayers' decisions. Thus, although statistical results show insignificance, theoretically and empirically there is still considerable room for service quality to be continuously improved as part of the government's strategy to increase taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations on an ongoing basis.

The Effect of Tax Penalties on Tax Compliance

Based on the tests conducted, the tax penalty variable (X4) shows a positive and significant effect on tax compliance with a regression coefficient of 0.211 and significance of less than 0.001 and a t-value of $4.126 > t\text{-table } 1.984$. These results indicate that the application of effective sanctions can encourage individual taxpayers to fulfill their tax obligations, as the existence of clear and consistent law enforcement mechanisms can be an external motivating factor.

These results indicate that individual taxpayers registered with the West Mataram Tax Office are aware of the impact of tax penalties, both administrative and criminal. Thus, based on this ratio, it appears that individual taxpayers registered with the West Mataram Tax Office have a better understanding of tax penalties than female taxpayers.

These results are consistent with research conducted by Alfiyah & Latifah (2017) and Rahmayanti et al. (2020), which found that tax penalties have an effect on the fulfillment of individual taxpayer obligations. This is because taxpayers will reconsider if they do not fulfill their tax obligations correctly and on time, as severe penalties await them.

In terms of tax payments, taxpayers will comply if they believe that tax penalties will cause them more harm. The more tax arrears taxpayers have to pay, the more difficult it will be for them to settle their debts. Although taxpayers do not receive any rewards for complying with their tax obligations, they will be punished if they neglect or deliberately fail to fulfill their tax obligations. Therefore, it is not surprising that this study found that

taxpayers' attitudes towards tax penalties were increasingly positive. Thus, tax penalties can increase taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations.

The influence of understanding tax regulations on the fulfillment of tax obligations is moderated by the role of tax consultants.

Based on the results of the Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) that has been conducted, it can be concluded that understanding of tax regulations moderated by the role of tax consultants has no effect on the fulfillment of tax obligations. This is indicated by a t-value of -1.210, which is smaller than the t-table value of 1.984, and a significance value of 0.229, which is greater than 0.05. Thus, there is no significant effect between understanding of tax regulations moderated by the role of tax consultants and the fulfillment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers registered at the West Mataram Tax Office.

These results indicate that although understanding tax regulations (X1) has a direct influence on compliance with tax obligations, the role of tax consultants (Z) as a moderating variable has not been able to significantly moderate this influence. In this context, the role of tax consultants has not yet functioned as a strengthening or weakening variable that modifies the effect of understanding on compliance behavior. This means that taxpayers view tax consultants as merely resolving technical matters related to calculating and reporting their tax obligations. Meanwhile, taxpayers already have the internal capacity to change taxpayer behavior. This is consistent with the results of direct testing of the variable of understanding tax regulations on individual taxpayer compliance.

Theoretically, these results reflect that although tax consultants have the potential to provide direction and guidance in understanding complex tax regulations, in practice, their role has not been optimal in creating a moderating influence on taxpayer behavior. Factors such as limited interaction, communication quality, or taxpayers' perceptions of the role of consultants may influence the effectiveness of this moderating role.

Thus, it can be said that understanding tax regulations is a fundamental aspect in fulfilling tax obligations. However, in this study, the role of tax consultants as moderators was not able to significantly moderate its influence. This is likely due to the complex and frequently changing nature of tax regulations, so that even though tax consultants provide guidance, the effectiveness of delivery and taxpayer understanding remains limited. Furthermore, in practice, taxpayers may rely more on personal experience or information from other sources than on tax consultants, so that the moderating role of consultants becomes less dominant or the role of tax consultants is limited to implementing technical administrative tasks such as calculations and reporting and is even only needed in the event of a tax dispute.

The influence of willingness to pay taxes on the fulfilment of tax obligations is moderated by the role of tax consultants.

Based on the results of the Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA), the interaction between willingness to pay taxes and the role of tax consultants showed a t-value of 1.222,

which was smaller than the t-table value of 1.984, with a significance value of 0.225, which was greater than 0.05. This indicates that the role of tax consultants has not been able to significantly moderate the effect of willingness to pay taxes on the fulfillment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers registered at the West Mataram Tax Office. Although willingness to pay taxes itself has a strong positive effect on the fulfillment of tax obligations, the role of tax consultants has not served to reinforce this effect.

These results may reflect that the role of consultants is still limited in providing motivation or psychological support that influences taxpayers' intentions to fulfill their tax obligations, or is limited to the technical implementation of tax administration. The willingness to pay taxes is a strong internal motivation that stems from the awareness and values of individual taxpayers. Therefore, the role of tax consultants has not been able to significantly moderate this influence because the willingness to pay taxes is more influenced by psychological and social factors inherent in the individual, not just technical consultation or administrative assistance from consultants. Tax consultants tend to play a role in the technical aspects of compliance, while the motivation to pay taxes requires a more personal approach and ethical values, which have not been fully addressed by the role of consultants.

The Effect of Tax Office Service Quality on Tax Compliance Is Moderated by the Role of Tax Consultants

The results of the MRA test analysis of the interaction between the quality of tax office services and the role of tax consultants show a t-value of -0.487, which is still far below the t-table value of 1.984, and a significance value of 0.628, which is much greater than 0.05. Thus, this interaction has no significant effect on the fulfillment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers registered at the West Mataram Tax Office. These results indicate that the role of tax consultants has not been able to moderate the effect of tax office service quality on the fulfillment of tax obligations. This may be due to the misalignment of functions between service providers and consultants, resulting in a lack of moderation effectiveness.

The quality of tax office services should directly influence the level of taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations. However, the role of tax consultants has not been effective in moderating the influence of this variable, possibly due to a lack of synergy or effective coordination between tax consultants and tax offices. Tax consultants operate independently and do not always interact directly with tax office service mechanisms. Thus, the moderating effect of tax consultants on service quality as a factor influencing the fulfillment of individual taxpayers' tax obligations is not yet apparent, as these two functions operate relatively separately and may even face each other in court in the event of a tax dispute.

The Effect of Tax Penalties on Tax Compliance Is Moderated by the Role of Tax Consultants

The interaction between tax penalties and the role of tax consultants also showed insignificant results, with a t-value of 0.861 and significance of 0.392, both of which did not meet the significance criteria ($p < 0.05$ and $t\text{-value} > t\text{-table } 1.984$). This indicates that

the role of tax consultants has not been able to moderate the effect of tax penalties on the fulfillment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers registered with the West Mataram Tax Office. Although tax penalties themselves have a positive and significant effect on the fulfillment of tax obligations, the role of tax consultants has not been able to increase this effect.

Tax penalties are an external factor that clearly has a positive influence on the fulfillment of individual taxpayers' tax obligations through tangible consequences. However, tax consultants have not been able to significantly moderate the influence of these penalties, which means that tax consultants play a greater role in consultation on prevention and voluntary compliance than in punishment. Tax consultants have not been able to control the impact of tax penalties on the fulfillment of tax obligations because their duties are usually preventive and educational in nature, rather than directly reinforcing repressive penalties.

Conclusion

Understanding tax regulations has a positive effect on the fulfillment of individual taxpayers' tax obligations. This shows that taxpayers' understanding of tax regulations can increase their compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations.

The willingness to pay taxes has a positive effect on the fulfillment of individual taxpayers' tax obligations. This shows that the willingness to pay taxes can increase taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations.

The quality of tax office services has an impact on the fulfillment of individual taxpayer obligations. This shows that the quality of services provided by tax officials is not able to improve taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations.

Tax penalties have a positive effect on the fulfillment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers. This shows that tax penalties are able to increase taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations.

The role of tax consultants has no influence in moderating the influence of variables such as understanding of tax regulations, willingness to pay taxes, quality of tax office services, and tax penalties on the fulfillment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers. This shows that the role of tax consultants is unable to moderate the influence of these independent variables on taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations.

Implications, Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

There are three implications in the results of this study, namely theoretical implications, practical implications and policy implications. The theoretical implications of these findings support the Theory of Planned Behavior, which is evidenced by the positive relationship between understanding tax regulations and willingness to pay taxes, and the fulfillment of tax obligations by individual taxpayers. Furthermore, it also supports attribution theory, as evidenced by the relationship between understanding tax regulations, willingness to pay taxes, quality of tax office services, and tax penalties with the fulfillment of tax obligations. Furthermore, it confirms the Awareness Theory and

Compliance Theory, which emphasize the role of legal awareness and perceptions of institutional services in shaping tax compliance behavior. Overall, these results reinforce the understanding that tax compliance is more influenced by complex interactions between internal and external factors, where a purely technical approach (such as tax consultation) is not sufficient to significantly improve compliance behavior.

The practical implications of this research are that the Indonesian Directorate General of Taxes should consider that individual taxpayer compliance is influenced by internal factors such as understanding of tax regulations and willingness to pay taxes, as well as external factors such as tax sanctions. Meanwhile, the quality of tax office services is not capable of improving individual taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations. Similarly, the presence of tax consultants has not been able to moderate its influence on taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their tax obligations.

The policy implications of this research can be used as consideration for policy makers, especially the government, in this case the Ministry of Finance and the Directorate General of Taxes of the Republic of Indonesia, to continue to improve taxpayers' understanding of personal taxation regulations through ongoing education, maintain taxpayer compliance by providing incentives for compliant taxpayers, maintain tax penalties, and evaluate the services provided.

The limitations of this study are as follows:(1) Respondents consisted of only one tax office, so the results do not fully reflect conditions in other regions; (2) moderating variables did not show a significant effect, requiring retesting to consider the quality and level of utilization of tax consultancy services; and (3) additional variables such as psychological factors and the use of digital taxation technology were not included.

Given these limitations, further research is recommended to: (a) expand the coverage area and sample size so that the research results are more representative; (b) add new variables such as the use of digital technology, psychological aspects, and variables that measure the effectiveness of interactions between taxpayers, consultants, and tax authorities; and (c) consider a qualitative approach to explore more deeply the perceptions, motivations, and awareness of taxpayers regarding their tax obligations. In addition, for quantitative research, it is recommended that when distributing questionnaires to respondents, someone accompany them while they fill out the questionnaire to ensure that they understand each question item.

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